

ISic0819

I.Sicily inscription 0819

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Noto, Biblioteca comunale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644908

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1964.0158

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique.* At 1964.0627

Manganaro, G. 1962. Graffiti e iscrizioni funerarie della Sicilia orientale. *Helikon.* 2: 485-501. At fig.5-6

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